

FORMATION OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE BY MEANS OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE COMMUNICATION

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Annotation: Foreign language communicative competence can be defined as the ability to solve communicative tasks in a specific framework of many communicative situations. This article is about the formation of professional competence by means of foreign language communication.

Keywords: foreign language communicative competence, professional training of specialists, competence-based approach, communication skills, student's professional competence.

Professional communicative competence implies the ability of a specialist to realize the knowledge acquired in the process of learning, skills and abilities to ensure effective direct (with understanding by hearing and speaking) and mediated (when reading and writing) professional communication. Competence-based approach to the definition of goals and content of education makes it possible to highlight the importance of forming professional communicative competence in training a specialist not only as a basis for formation of the competent, cultural professional, but also as a tool for acquiring future professional skills that allow to apply knowledge gained in various fields in practice.

Foreign language naturally is one of the main means of formation of professional communicative competence of the student as it is an integrative subject and learning a foreign language involves the concentration and integration of language and special knowledge.

Knowledge of a foreign language is not only an attribute of a person's cultural development, but also a condition for person's successful activity in various spheres of industrial and social life. The criterion of the effectiveness of real communication

is its productivity, the achievement of mutually beneficial results. Foreign language is used in the process of working with foreign companies, in communication at various professional conferences, in personal contact. The ability to adapt to new information means; to be ready to participate in international professional communications; the ability to adapt to the conditions of the modern labor market - these are the qualities that are formed in the process of developing foreign language communicative competence. They determine the competitive advantage of graduates of a modern university, ensure their career growth, and contribute to their life success. It is obvious that the formation of foreign language communicative competence is one of the important aspects of professional training of specialists.

In modern linguistics the communicative competence refers to the possession of linguistic competence, i.e. mastering a certain amount of information of language material, the ability to correlate language means with the tasks and conditions of communication, as well as the ability to organize speech communication taking into account social norms of behavior and the communicative expediency of the statement.

The structure of professional foreign language communicative competence is quite complex and includes not only the linguistic component (possession of means of speech communication), the information component (professional competence), but also the cultural component (background knowledge of communication partners and realities belonging to another culture). Communicative competence is the interaction of the fundamental systems of knowledge and skills necessary for the implementation of communication.

The formation of foreign language communicative competence is aimed at developing the ability to practically use real, living language and is designed to teach the conscious correlation of linguistic phenomena with their communicative functions: informative, regulatory, emotionally assessed and etiquette.

In the course of the implementation of these functions, appropriate communication skills are formed: - information request, reporting of information, perception and understanding of the perceived information; - motivation to something, a request for something, advice, an agreement on something, a perception of motivation and a reaction to it; - expression of opinion, assessment, feelings, emotions, belief, expression of pleasure / displeasure; - address, the beginning of a conversation, an expression of interest in the interlocutor, the maintenance of a conversation, the end of a conversation, congratulations, thanks, an expression of sympathy [1].

For the successful realization of these functions by means of a foreign language, it is necessary to own these means, to be able to use them in the main types of speech activity, to know regional geographic realities, features of speech and non-speech behavior in a socio-cultural context.

The formation of foreign language communicative competence, as one of the main goals of teaching a foreign language in higher education, is a means of achieving another, common goal - the development of a student's professional competence. Enriched by appropriate knowledge and skills in the process of educational and professional activities, foreign language communicative activity contributes to the development of students' communicative competence and ensures their successful professional activity in the future. Foreign language communicative competence should be considered as a resource quality, which serves as the basis for the formation of a professional and competent specialist and, therefore, should be taken into account when designing educational programs of the new generation.

Список литературы

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